

Revolutionizing Indian Agriculture with Drones: A Comprehensive Review of Applications, Challenges and Future Prospects

**Samik Kumar Pradhan ^{a++}, Debraj Nayek ^b,
Satyajit Muduli ^{c+}, Masoom Ankit Patel ^d,
Chitrasena Padhy ^{a++*} and Arindam Mandal ^e**

^a Department of Agricultural Extension Education, M. S. Swaminathan School of Agriculture, Centurion University of Technology and Management Paralakhemundi, Dist. Gajapati, Odisha, 761 211, India.

^b Department of Agronomy and Agroforestry, M. S. Swaminathan School of Agriculture, Centurion University of Technology and Management Paralakhemundi, Dist. Gajapati, Odisha, 761 211, India.

^c Department of Horticulture, M. S. Swaminathan School of Agriculture, Centurion University of Technology and Management, Paralakhemundi, Dist. Gajapati, Odisha, 761211, India.

^d Department of Seed science and Technology, Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University (A Central University), Uttarakhand, India.

^e Department of Agronomy and Agroforestry, School of Agriculture and Allied Sciences, The Neotia University, Sarisha, West Bengal, India.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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⁺⁺ Associate Professor;

*Corresponding author: E-mail: chitrasenapadhy@cutm.ac.in;

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ABSTRACT

Indian agriculture contributes to the GDP, but our nation still needs to improve productivity and efficiency to the fullest extent possible. Numerous aspects and concerns need to be identified, supported, and equipped with solutions. Now agriculture sector is the fastest-growing sector, which is faced with several issues, one of which is the lack of labour for farming. Some additional issues or challenges are extreme weather conditions, inadequate and ineffective fertilizer application, infection, illnesses, allergies, and other health issues brought on by chemical applications (fungicide, pesticide, insecticide, etc.). Drones, also called Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), have developed remarkably in recent years. Common applications of drones are Pesticide application, soil sampling and fertilizing, farm animal observation, real-time aerial imagery, sensor data collection, etc. These drones have been primarily created to speed up, boost productivity, and effectively utilize agricultural resources. The government is working toward a liberalized policy to encourage drones and also provide institutions, individual farmers, and businesses with significant financial incentives to buy and utilize or build drones. If farmers start to trust drones for spray-related tasks, there's a strong chance their use will be expanded to other revolutionary use cases as well, which will be beneficial for Indian agriculture.

Keywords: Drone; agriculture; irrigation; crop monitoring.

1. INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector is increasingly leveraging technological advancements to enhance productivity and sustainability. Among these innovations, drone technology, a crucial component of precision agriculture, is gaining global recognition (Murugan et al., 2024). Drones give farmers a bird's-eye perspective of agricultural fields, permitting them to collect precise information on crop health, moisture content, pest infestations, and other topics (Anusha and Padhy, 2024). Traditional manual agriculture methods might be completely transformed by drone technology, which is an enormous advance (Pathak et al., 2020). Globally, agricultural companies are increasingly using drone technology to modernise farming (Duncan et al., 2021). In addition to having a satellite navigation system, programmable controller, propulsion system, automated flight planning capabilities, and the capacity to carry payloads such as cameras, spraying systems, etc., drones are remotely piloted aircraft systems (RPAS) (Gupta et al., 2013). Other acronyms that are often used interchangeably include unmanned aerial vehicle/systems (UAV/UAVs) and unmanned aircraft systems (UAS); nonetheless, RPAS is the most official and widely used method to refer to such a system (Pathak et al., 2020). Drones, which stand for "Dynamic Remotely Operated Navigation Equipment," are flying machines that can fly themselves along a predefined path utilising GPS coordinates and autopilot control (Ajmera et al., 2022). As an alternative, it may be manually

controlled via radio signals via smartphone apps or remote control (Maddikunta et al., 2021). Drones can locate items that are undetectable to the human eye because they have access to so many sensors. Drones can, therefore deliver real-time, more accurate, reliable, and objective information with greater detail and fewer errors (Molina et al., 2012). Drones can fly autonomously with dedicated software which allows making a flight plan and deploying the system with GPS and feed in various parameters such as speed, altitude, ROI (Region of Interest), geo-fence and fail-safe modes. Drones are preferred over full size aircrafts due to major factors like combination of high spatial resolution and fast turnaround capabilities together with low operation cost and easy to trigger. These features are required in precision agriculture where large areas are monitored and analyses are carried out in minimum time (Dutta & Goswami, 2020; Singh et al., 2024; Meivel & Maheswari, 2021).

A drone used for agricultural purposes is referred to as an agriculture drone. Particularly in difficult terrain like hills, drones might be utilised to spray pesticides more efficiently than time-consuming, conventional approaches (Yinka-Banjo & Ajayi, 2019). Artificial intelligence and machine learning may be used to analyse soil conditions and forecast crop output using high-resolution drone photographs taken using NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) imaging technology (Saini et al., nd). Using image processing techniques, a stressed plant may be independently discovered and inspected (Du &

Sun, 2004). Using this discovery as a guide, farmers may take preventive measures to limit diseases from spreading to other crops (Reinecke & Prinsloo, 2017). Timely measures can be taken to minimise the effects of climate change and unpredictable weather, optimise fertilisation, rationalise irrigation, and stop losses from biotic stresses like insects, pests, and disease by using the insights analysed from data collected by drones and satellite-based remote sensing (Pathak et al., 2020). Farmers can make informed decisions regarding irrigation, fertiliser, and pesticide application by using real-time data gathered by drones. In addition to improving crop quality, this data-driven approach reduces resource waste and its negative effects on the environment. Drone technology and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) allow farmers to create detailed maps of their land (Anusha and Padhy, 2024).

2. DRONE OPERATIONS IN INDIAN AGRICULTURE

Drones are presently promoted in India as typical automatic spray devices that may be used for pesticides and other tasks (Beriya, 2022). Using a sprayer to cover plants reduces the health risks associated with hand spraying and saves time, resources, and labour (Chaitanya et al., 2020). According to the Indian Agriculture Ministry, each acre will cost between Rs 350 and Rs 450 for the use of a drone with a 10 km payload capacity (Zeliang et al., 2017). The figure is entirely predicated on the assumption that a drone equipped with several batteries will be used for at least six hours every afternoon to cover about 30 acres of agriculture (Shi et al., 2016). These were extracted from a fact-sharing webinar held by the company IFFCO Kisan, in which Dr. Shankar Goenka, a professional, gave information on drone operations based on their reports on the rollout of drone income in addition to spray services (on a rent-per-acre basis).

Digital innovations can assist developing countries for overcoming global poverty and hunger quicker in rural areas (Padhy et al, 2022). According to Dr. Goenka, even for vegetation with higher heights like sugarcane, mango orchards, and other similar flora, equal depth/unfold of spray is carried out using drones (Yadav et al., 2023). Due to automated processes, a reduction in the input prices of spray equipment (pesticides/weedicides) is predicted to be in the range of 25–30%). Using

nano urea as an example, if the farmer can save 25% on the price of the input while spraying it on an acre for Rs. 240 per bottle, the price is reduced to that level (Katekar et al., 2022). Due to the tiny droplet sizes of about 50 microns compared to the manual spray's droplet length of about 500 microns, a similar around eighty-nine per cent reduction in water is also achieved (Carlson et al., 1979). Drone sprays save time because each spray takes about 5-7 minutes per acre, but a person can normally only cover three to four acres manually in one afternoon. A 10-litre capacity drone has an 11-litre tank capacity, among other drone features (Beriya, 2022). The integration of drone technology has the potential to revolutionise the agricultural industry and pave the way for more effective, sustainable, and productive farming practices (Anusha & Padhy, 2024).

Drone can be used to measure forest biodiversity (Getzin et al., 2012) and biodiversity ecosystems safeguard us against natural calamities like floods and storms (Padhy et al., 2022).

3. DRONES IN AGRICULTURE APPLICATIONS

Drones can be used in a variety of agricultural applications, some of which are briefly covered below:

3.1 Field and Soil Analysis

Sensors that can measure the soil's moisture content, nutrients, fertility, and topography can be mounted on drones. The regional variability of crop growth and field conditions may therefore be taken into consideration when planning the pattern of planting various crops, scheduling irrigation, and managing fertiliser applications using these sensors (El Nahry et al., 2011). Soil analysis is required to ensure better productivity (Padhy et al, 2021).

3.2 Planting of Seed Pods

Several companies have created additional drone system attachments that can fire pods containing seed and plant nutrients into already prepared soil, even though they were invented but rarely used. Lower planting expenses result from this (Katekar et al., 2022).

3.3 Crop Monitoring

Throughout the agricultural season, drones may be used to monitor crop conditions, enabling

timely and need-based management. Yield loss can be prevented with a timely and appropriate reaction (Anghelache et al., 2021). This technology will eliminate the need for farmers to visually inspect their crops. The combination of large regions and ineffective crop monitoring is the primary farming problem (Tian et al., 2020). Unpredictable weather conditions make monitoring more difficult and raise risk and field maintenance expenses (Elijah et al., 2018).

3.4 Identification of Weeds

Drones may be used to detect the presence of weeds in the field. These weeds might be quickly removed from the field so they don't compete with the main crop for resources (Herwitz et al., 2004).

3.5 Crop Spraying

In order to achieve consistent coverage, drones can precisely distribute liquid while changing their distance from the ground and spraying in real-time. Improved efficacy and reduced chemical penetration into groundwater were the final results (Delavarpour et al., 2021). Experts claim that drones can actually carry out aerial spraying up to five times faster than traditional equipment (Klauser & Pauschunger, 2021).

3.6 Irrigation

Drones using thermal, multispectral, or hyperspectral sensors can employ multispectral indices to identify deficient moisture locations in the field. This facilitates the accurate and timely scheduling of irrigation for the assigned areas (Abrahams et al., 2023).

3.7 Crop Health Monitoring

Depending on their health and stress level, plants reflect different amounts of visible and near-infrared light (Zahir et al., 2022). Crop health can be tracked over time and remedial measures can be more successful when drones are fitted with sensors that can scan crops using visible and near-infrared light (Hafeez et al., 2022).

3.8 Weed, Insect, Pest, and Disease Control

Drones may identify and alert farmers to field regions affected by weeds, disease, and insect

pests in addition to soil conditions (Sinha & Dhanalakshmi, 2022). Based on this knowledge, farmers can reduce costs and improve the health of their fields by maximizing the use of chemicals needed to combat pests (Brodt et al., 2011).

3.9 Protecting the field from Animal Damage

The thermal cameras that are put on drones may find people or animals in the dark. Therefore, it can be used to safeguard fields from animal damage that would otherwise be impossible to notice at night in huge fields (Patel et al., 2022). It will therefore function more effectively than human guards.

3.10 Scaring Birds

After planting the seeds of various crops, birds pose the biggest challenge. To keep the field protected, labour is required. Birds in fields can be scared off with a few drone flights (Cheke & Sidatt, 2019).

4. GENERAL DRONE LAWS IN INDIA

India allows the usage of drones, however, there are a number of drone regulations that must be followed when flying there (Ahirwar et al., 2019). A remote pilot licence issued by DGCA is mandatory for operating any drone, except for drones up to 2 kg weight (used for non-commercial purposes) and drones weighing less than 250 grams (Drone Rules, 2021). When operating a drone in India that weighs more than 250 grams, operators need to make sure they abide by the following drone legislation (Jain & Saxena, 2020).

- Avoid flying your drone over crowded places or regions with a lot of people (Whitlock, 2014).
- When using your drone, respect the privacy of others (Finn & Wright, 2016).
- Do not fly your drone within 5 km of airports or in areas where aeroplanes are operating (Pathak et al., 2020).
- You may only fly in excellent weather and during the hours of daylight (Ahirwar et al., 2019).
- Flying a drone in sensitive regions, such as inside military or government buildings, is prohibited (Yaacoub et al., 2020).
- You have to have finished a training program and be no less than 18 years old.

- Each drone has to have a license plate with the operator's name and contact details (Ahirwar et al., 2019).
- A single UAV can be flown at once (Merkert et al., 2021).
- No Unmanned Aircraft System (UAS) shall be allowed to fly within 25 kilometres from the international border including the Line of Control (LoC), Line of Actual Control (LAC) and Actual Ground Position Line (AGPL) (Ministry of civil aviation, 2021).
- Never take your drone within 500 meters out to sea from the shore (Darack, 2012).
- Flying is prohibited in Delhi within 5 km of Vijay Chowk.
- Flying above national parks and wildlife sanctuaries is not advised.
- Every drone needs liability insurance (Ahirwar et al., 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

The usage of drones can offer to businesses, and entrepreneurial opportunities for drone industries (Das et al, 2023) and entrepreneurship has long been recognised as a powerful driver of economic growth (Pattanayak and Padhy, 2022). The drones are revolutionizing the way we grow our food, helping farming for more efficient doing more sustainable and productive (Precision Ag Services, 2024) ; 21st century, entrepreneurship underwent a thoughtful transformation (Mishra et al, 2023). Farmers are not using the recommended dose of fertilizers in cotton cultivation (Padhy et al, 2021); drone spray technology can help for precise application of fertilisers (ICL, 2024). Drones have great potential to transform Indian agriculture. The production of drones is projected to become less expensive in the future as technology advances. Farmers are facing multifaceted psychological challenges (Padhy and Raju, 2019) and drones can help farmers for increasing the agricultural productivity (McCarthy et al, 2023) Drone technology has the potential to transform agriculture by providing an alternative to manual activities (Katekar and Cheruku, 2022) so that farmers can get extra time for fun and frolic, have time to do something one enjoys, and keep socially connected (Padhy and Raju, 2018), Drones provide superior and more precise aerial images over agricultural regions compared to satellite imagery. Programs for identifying weeds and diseases, assessing soil characteristics, identifying vegetation variations, and producing precise elevation models may now also make

use of drones. Farmers will be able to better understand their farms due to drones. As a consequence, farmers may use less pesticides and produce healthier food. Nearly every farmer who has utilised drones has benefited in some way. By getting rid of pests before they destroy entire harvests, optimising irrigation for plants that are stressed by heat, modifying the soil to promote development in areas of trouble, and putting out fires before they get out of control, they may make better use of their land. Therefore, by assisting farmers in more efficient and sustainable land and resource management, drones may potentially play a significant role in agriculture in the future.

DISCLAIMER (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE)

Author(s) hereby declare that generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models, etc have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript. This explanation will include the name, version, model, and source of the generative AI technology and as well as all input prompts provided to the generative AI technology.

Details of the AI usage are given below:

- 1.Quillbot
2. HAS

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

- Abrahams, M., Sibanda, M., Dube, T., Chimonyo, V. G., & Mabhaudhi, T. (2023). A systematic review of UAV applications for mapping neglected and underutilised crop species' spatial distribution and health. *Remote Sensing*, 15(19), 4672.
- Ahirwar, S., Swarnkar, R., Bhukya, S., & Namwade, G. (2019). Application of drone in agriculture. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*, 8(01), 2500-2505.
- Ajmera, D., Saroliya, M., & Arora, P. (2022). Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs). *International Research Journal of Innovations in Engineering and Technology*, 6(1), 22.
- Anghelache, D., Persu, C., Dumitru, D., & Bălțatu, C. (2021). Intelligent monitoring of

- diseased plants using drones. *Annals of the University of Craiova-Agriculture, Montanology, Cadastre Series*, 51(2), 146-151.
- Anusha, B., & Padhy, C. (2024). Scientific use of drone technology for better farming. *International Journal of Agricultural Extension and Social Development*, 7(3), 113-116.
- Beriya, A. (2022). Application of drones in Indian agriculture (No. 73). ICT India Working Paper.
- Brodthorn, S., Six, J., Feenstra, G., Ingels, C., & Campbell, D. (2011). Sustainable agriculture. *Nat. Educ. Knowl*, 3(1).
- Carlson, R., Vidaver, A., Wysong, D., Riesselman, J., Lenné, J., Leath, K., ... & Carter, W. (1979). SA Ostazeski, J.H. Elgin, Jr. *The Plant Disease Reporter*, 63, 711.
- Chaitanya, P., Kotte, D., Srinath, A., & Kalyan, K. B. (2020). Development of smart pesticide spraying robot. *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering*, 8(5), 2193-2202.
- Cheke, R. A., & Sidatt, M. E. H. (2019). A review of alternatives to fenthion for quelea bird control. *Crop Protection*, 116, 15-23.
- Darack, E. (2012). UAVs: The new frontier for weather research and prediction. *Weatherwise*, 65(2), 20-27.
- Das, A.K, Singh, B. , Rathore, Kumar,K. (2023). Drones Usage Opportunities For Entrepreneurs Contributing Towards Aatmanirbar Bharat. *SMS Journal of Entrepreneurship & Innovation*, 10(Issue-1), 24-36.
- Delavarpour, N., Koparan, C., Nowatzki, J., Bajwa, S., & Sun, X. (2021). A technical study on UAV characteristics for precision agriculture applications and associated practical challenges. *Remote Sensing*, 13(6), 1204.
- Drone Rules, 2021, Government of India, Ministry of Civil Aviation, Lok Sabha Unstarred Question No. 834. [https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/177/AU834.pdf?source=pqals#:~:text=The%20salient%20details%20of%20the,Unique%20identification%20Number%20\(UIN\).&text=issuance%20of%20remote%20pilot%20licences,DGCA%20within%20specified%20time%20limits.](https://sansad.in/getFile/loksabhaquestions/annex/177/AU834.pdf?source=pqals#:~:text=The%20salient%20details%20of%20the,Unique%20identification%20Number%20(UIN).&text=issuance%20of%20remote%20pilot%20licences,DGCA%20within%20specified%20time%20limits.)
- Du, C. J., & Sun, D. W. (2004). Recent developments in the applications of image processing techniques for food quality evaluation. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 15(5), 230-249.
- Duncan, E., Abdulai, A. R., & Fraser, E. D. (2021). Modernizing agriculture through digital technologies: Prospects and challenges. *Handbook on the Human Impact of Agriculture*, 138-161.
- Dutta, G., & Goswami, P. (2020). Application of drone in agriculture: A review. *International Journal of Chemical Studies*, 8(5), 181-187.
- El Nahry, A. H., Ali, R. R., & El Baroudy, A. A. (2011). An approach for precision farming under pivot irrigation system using remote sensing and GIS techniques. *Agricultural Water Management*, 98(4), 517-531.
- Elijah, O., Rahman, T. A., Orikumhi, I., Leow, C. Y., & Hindia, M. N. (2018). An overview of Internet of Things (IoT) and data analytics in agriculture: Benefits and challenges. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 5(5), 3758-3773.
- Finn, R. L., & Wright, D. (2016). Privacy, data protection and ethics for civil drone practice: A survey of industry, regulators, and civil society organisations. *Computer Law & Security Review*, 32(4), 577-586.
- Getzin S, Wiegand K, Schoening I. Assessing biodiversity in forests using very high-resolution images and unmanned aerial vehicles. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 2012;3:397–404. doi: 10.1111/j.2041-210X.2011.00158.x. [DOI] [Google Scholar]
- Gupta, S. G., Ghonge, D. M., & Jawandhiya, P. M. (2013). Review of unmanned aircraft system (UAS). *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Engineering & Technology (IJARCET)*, 2, 1-5.
- Hafeez, A., Husain, M. A., Singh, S. P., Chauhan, A., Khan, M. T., Kumar, N., ... & Soni, S. K. (2022). Implementation of drone technology for farm monitoring & pesticide spraying: A review. *Information Processing in Agriculture*.
- Herwitz, S. R., Johnson, L. F., Dunagan, S. E., Higgins, R. G., Sullivan, D. V., Zheng, J., ... & Brass, J. A. (2004). Imaging from an unmanned aerial vehicle: Agricultural surveillance and decision support. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 44(1), 49-61.
- ICL, 2024, Drone Spray Technology, <https://icl-growingsolutions.com/agriculture/categories/drone-spray-technology/>.

- Jain, A., & Saxena, A. (2020). Regulation and operation of drones: A threat to privacy. *Issue 4 Int'l JL Mgmt. & Human*, 3, 1945.
- Katekar, V., & Cheruku, J. K. (2022). The application of drone technology for sustainable agriculture in India. *Current Agriculture Research Journal*, 10(3).
- Klauser, F., & Pauschinger, D. (2021). Entrepreneurs of the air: Sprayer drones as mediators of volumetric agriculture. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 84, 55-62.
- Maddikunta, P. K. R., Hakak, S., Alazab, M., Bhattacharya, S., Gadekallu, T. R., Khan, W. Z., & Pham, Q. V. (2021). Unmanned aerial vehicles in smart agriculture: Applications, requirements, and challenges. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 21(16), 17608-17619.
- McCarthy, C., Nyoni, Y., Kachamba, D. J., Banda, L. B., Moyo, B., Chisambi, C., ... & Hoshino, B. (2023). Can drones help smallholder farmers improve agriculture efficiencies and reduce food insecurity in Sub-Saharan Africa? Local perceptions from Malawi. *Agriculture*, 13(5), 1075.
- Meivel, S., & Maheswari, S. (2021). Remote sensing analysis of agricultural drone. *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing*, 49(3), 689-701.
- Merkert, R., Beck, M. J., & Bushell, J. (2021). Will it fly? Adoption of the road pricing framework to manage drone use of airspace. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 150, 156-170.
- Ministry of Civil Aviation, 2021, No Drones Allowed within 25 Km of International Borders: Centre, <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/no-drones-allowed-within-25-km-of-international-borders-centre-2503808>.
- Mishra, P., Padhy, C., Mishra, N., Roy, D., Prasanna, V., & Madhuri, C. R. (2023). 21st Century Entrepreneurship Challenges and Opportunities. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 41(12), 196-202.
- Molina, P., Colomina, I., Vitoria, T., Silva, P. F., Skaloud, J., Kornus, W., ... & Aguilera, C. (2012). Searching lost people with UAVs: The system and results of the close-search project. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 39, 441-446.
- Murugan P.P, Dhivya C, and Senthil kumar M. 2024. "Farmers Awareness and Perception of Drone Technology". *Journal of Experimental Agriculture International* 46 (10):426-35. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jeai/2024/v46i102965>.
- Padhy, C., & Raju, P. S. (2018). Stress among farmers and its alleviation. *Int J Manag Technol Eng*, 8(12), 2882-7.
- Padhy, C., & Raju, P. S. (2019). Psychological problems faced by farmers and suggested remedies. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology*, 7(1), 2715-2719.
- Padhy, C., Raju, P. S., & Raj, R. K. (2021). Constraints in Cotton cultivation reported by growers and suggestive measures. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 39(2), 118-125.
- Padhy, C., Raju, P. S., & Raj, R. K. (2021). Cotton crop management practices adopted in a tribal region of Odisha. *Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci*, 10(1), 811-9.
- Padhy, C., Reddy, M. D., Raj, R. K., & Pattanayak, K. P. (2022). Role of digital technology in agriculture. *Indian Journal of Natural Sciences*, 13(71), 40287-40290.
- P. P., M., C., D., & M., S. (2024). Farmers awareness and perception of drone technology. *Journal of Experimental Agriculture International*, 46(10), 426-435. <https://doi.org/10.9734/jeai/2024/v46i102965>
- Patel, R. R., Mishra, B. P., Chaubey, C., Maurya, R. K., & Pathak, D. K. (2022). Chapter-8 drone in agriculture: Application, challenges, and future perspective. *Modern Concepts in Farming*, 95.
- Pathak, H., Kumar, G., Mohapatra, S. D., Gaikwad, B. B., & Rane, J. (2020). Use of drones in agriculture: Potentials, problems, and policy needs. ICAR-National Institute of Abiotic Stress Management, 300, 4-15.
- Pattanayak, K. P., & Padhy, C. (2022). Entrepreneurs' Contributions to Economic Development and Growth. *Indian Journal of Natural Sciences*, 13(71), 976-997.
- Precision Ag Services, 2024, Farming in the 21st Century: The role of agricultural drones, <https://precisionagservices.com.au/farming-in-the-21st-century-the-role-of-agricultural-drones/>.
- Reinecke, M., & Prinsloo, T. (2017, July). The influence of drone monitoring on crop health and harvest size. In *2017 1st International Conference on Next*

- Generation Computing Applications (NextComp)* (pp. 5-10). IEEE.
- Saini, A., Singh, G., & Guleria, A. (2024). Remote sensing and its modern applications in agriculture. *Chapter 13*.
- Shi, Y., Thomasson, J. A., Murray, S. C., Pugh, N. A., Rooney, W. L., Shafian, S., ... & Yang, C. (2016). Unmanned aerial vehicles for high-throughput phenotyping and agronomic research. *PLOS ONE*, *11*(7), e0159781.
- Singh, N., Gupta, D., Joshi, M., Yadav, K., Nayak, S., Kumar, M., Nayak, K., Gulaiya, S., & Rajpoot, A. S. (2024). Application of drones technology in agriculture: A modern approach. *J. Sci. Res. Rep.*, *30*(7), 142-145.
<https://journaljsrr.com/index.php/JSRR/article/view/2131>
- Sinha, B. B., & Dhanalakshmi, R. (2022). Recent advancements and challenges of Internet of Things in smart agriculture: A survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, *126*, 169-184.
- Tian, H., Wang, T., Liu, Y., Qiao, X., & Li, Y. (2020). Computer vision technology in agricultural automation—a review. *Information Processing in Agriculture*, *7*(1), 1-19.
- Whitlock, C. (2014). Part one: War zones when drones fall from the sky. *Washington Post*.
- Yaacoub, J. P., Noura, H., Salman, O., & Chehab, A. (2020). Security analysis of drone systems: Attacks, limitations, and recommendations. *Internet of Things*, *11*, 100218.
- Yadav, S., Choudhary, S., & Dhakar, D. (2023). Drone: Its importance in Indian agriculture. *Emerging Trends in Agriculture and Allied Sciences*, *50*.
- Yinka-Banjo, C., & Ajayi, O. (2019). Sky-farmers: Applications of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) in agriculture. *Autonomous Vehicles*, 107-128.
- Zahir, S. A. D. M., Omar, A. F., Jamlos, M. F., Azmi, M. A. M., & Muncan, J. (2022). A review of visible and near-infrared (Vis-NIR) spectroscopy application in plant stress detection. *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, *338*, 113468.
- Zeliang, P. K., Kikon, Z. J., Mawthoh, P., & Rajkova, D. J. (2017). Agricultural marketing and entrepreneurship development for farmers of Peren district.

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